

Research

Supply Chain Management Process of Readymade Garments Industry of Bangladesh: A Study on Standard Group

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Abstract: This thesis investigates the supply chain management (SCM) processes of Bangladesh's Readymade Garments (RMG) industry, specifically focusing on the Standard Group. The study explores how SCM is integrated into the RMG value chain, highlighting the complexities and risks involved, especially in manufacturing. By adopting a holistic view, the research examines the interactions between manufacturers, suppliers, and other stakeholders, emphasizing the importance of coordination and sustainability. The study uses primary and secondary data, with 50 respondents including merchandisers, suppliers, and quality controllers. A descriptive analysis was conducted using Likert's Summative Rating scale to evaluate key performance indicators in production, inventory management, forecasting, communication, order placement, and distribution. Findings reveal that while the Standard Group demonstrates strong performance in production and distribution, there are areas for improvement in forecasting accuracy and supplier communication. The results underscore the significance of efficient SCM in enhancing overall performance and responsiveness in the RMG industry.

Keywords: Standard Group, client, clothing washing, printing.

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Introduction

This thesis paper focuses on the supply chain management process of the Ready-made Garments Industry in Bangladesh, specifically on the Standard Group. The production of Ready-Made Garments (RMG) is a fitting illustration of Supply Chain Management (SCM). As an illustration, a developed country like Spain handles the design and development process, while a developing country like China supplies the raw materials. Production occurs in a Least Developed Country (LDC) like Bangladesh, and the final goods are then distributed to other developed and developing nations globally. In the RMG business value chain, manufacturing is positioned at the bottom tier and has the highest risk. Therefore, the manufacturing function was neither fixed nor constant in any certain place or nation. Supply chain management (SCM) encompasses the streamlined oversight of the whole product creation process, from procuring raw materials to manufacturing, shipping, and final delivery to the end customer. Supply Chain Management is the

organized management and execution of processes required to control the movement of materials, information, and financial resources in various activities, including demand planning, sourcing, production, inventory management, storage, transportation, logistics, and handling of excess or defective products. Efficient supply chain management is dependent on the formulation of a well-defined business plan, the use of specialized software, and the active engagement between different stakeholders[1]. Because it is such a vast and complicated enterprise, all partners, including suppliers, manufacturers, and others, must interact with one another and collaborate to generate efficiencies, effectively manage risk, and swiftly adjust to changes. Moreover, sustainable procurement and the closely related concept of corporate social responsibility, which evaluates a company's impact on the environment and social well-being, are important focus areas for modern businesses. Contemporary companies prioritize supply chain sustainability, including environmental, social, and legal dimensions[2].

Background of the Study:

An effective supply chain management system facilitates the identification of suppliers and the customer demand that the business must meet. The system establishes a link among consumer demand, suppliers, and production plans, ensuring that the operation remains centred on meeting client expectations.[3] The supply chains include not just the manufacturer and suppliers but also the transporters, warehouses, retailers, and customers themselves. Supply Chain Management (SCM) is the systematic coordination of all corporate processes to ensure the smooth and efficient movement of products, services, and information in response to consumer demand. It also involves coordinating important activities inside the organization, including predicting future needs, acquiring resources, putting orders, fulfilling orders, purchasing, producing, and shipping. I start by adopting a holistic perspective on supply chain management, specifically examining the actions and implications for both manufacturers and service providers. I analyze the methods by which organizations handle their interactions with customers and suppliers[4]. Subsequently, I will analyze the significant operational and financial indicators of supply chain performance, and then proceed to evaluate different supply network designs and their strategic consequences. I will continue by examining the intricacies of supply networks and the management of supply chain operations. I will also demonstrate the implementation and execution of supply chain management (SCM) within Standard Group.

Methodology of the Study:

The data have been acquired both via primary and secondary methods. The research mostly relies on secondary data and exclusively on primary data. The study on Standard Group's Supply Chain Management Process in the Readymade Garments Industry of Bangladesh utilizes two categories of data: primary and secondary data.

Sampling and Sampling Unit

A total of 50 individuals have been selected at random for the interview process. In addition to two suppliers, the sample unit is comprised of five senior merchandisers, thirteen assistant merchandisers, fifteen trainee merchandisers, six production executives, three commercial executives, six quality controllers, and six quality coordinators[5].

Sampling Technique

This research is a descriptive analysis that has a sample size of 50 respondents. The response pool comprises senior merchandisers, assistant merchandisers, trainee merchandisers, quality controllers, commercial officers, and suppliers affiliated with Standard Group. The sample is selected using the non-probability convenience sampling approach.[6].

Overview of Standard Group

Standard Group, a prominent clothing company in Bangladesh, began operations in 1984[7]. Throughout the years, the organization has seen substantial growth in both its scale and consumer clientele. The firm has internal facilities for clothing washing, printing, embroidery, apparel design, garment testing, and manufacture of different accessories. Their garment manufacturing setup and services in Bangladesh are equipped with state-of-the-art technology. All of our production areas have been equipped with machinery imported from the US and Europe. Each machine has been carefully selected by our highly skilled industrial engineers to guarantee excellent quality and productivity. Our

activities are centred on quality. Their goal is to consistently provide the utmost level of excellence within a certain timeframe[8]. Their proficient team has undergone training to guarantee the attainment of quality for each request. Every single one of their products undergoes a meticulous quality inspection and approval procedure to guarantee that the manufacturing quality is consistently maintained at every stage.

Under the corporate administration of The Civil Engineers Limited, Standard Group started its garment and textile manufacturing operations in the year 84. While Bangladesh was experiencing a period of prosperity during the neo-industrial revolution, the development of the jute industry was a contributing factor. Two professionals who had just graduated from Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology (BUET) took the initiative to create The Civil Engineers Ltd. in the year 1969[9]. The Civil Engineers Ltd., which is employed in the construction industry, has been honored with a great number of honors and recognitions on a national scale. During the middle of the 1980s, as the garment revolution was beginning to emerge in the economy, Engineer Mosharraf Hussain and Engineer Rashid[10]. A significant step was taken by Atiqur Rahman in the direction of entering the clothing sector. As of right now, Standard Group is recognized as one of the most successful garment manufacturers across Bangladesh.

The Cost Advantage

The Cost Advantage Bangladesh is one of the least costly nations in the world for the manufacturing of garments owing to a number of variables, including the cheap cost of labour, the strong industry motivation, the government incentives, the absence of any import costs for garment accessories that are required, and as many other aspects as possible. It is possible to make use of these cost savings in order to achieve price and quality benefits and provide the highest possible value to our clients.

The Technological Advantage

For the purpose of garment manufacturing in Bangladesh, they have one of the most cutting-edge technological setups and providers of services. In every aspect of manufacturing, our machines have been brought from the United States and Europe. Our most skilled industrial engineers have carefully selected each piece of equipment, ensuring that it is of the highest quality and most productive throughout the whole production process[11].

The Quality Advantage

The Quality Advantage: We place a strong emphasis on quality in all of our business processes. They make it a priority to provide deliveries of the finest possible quality in a timely way. In order to guarantee that each and every order is of the highest possible quality, their expert team has been trained. Each and every one of their goods is put through a stringent quality control and approval procedure in order to further guarantee that the manufacturing quality is maintained at all levels[12].

Legal Compliance

In addition to adhering to the stringent compliance standards established by our clients all around the globe, Standard Group is committed to adhering to the legal requirements that have been established by the government of Bangladesh.

Safety Compliance

As a firm, Standard Group places a great priority on security and welfare, and we adhere to stringent safety compliance standards in order to guarantee the safety of all of our workers and protect the resources of the company. The rules governing safety include those pertaining to mobility, fire safety, worker health and safety, and a variety of other areas[13].

Product & Services

Woven Products:

Bottom

Within the country of Bangladesh, Standard Group has one of the most extensive bottom manufacturing facilities. They are capable of producing bottoms that range from basic bottoms to bottoms that are complicated and extremely trendy

(quite fashionable) [14]. It is possible for them to manufacture almost any kind of bottom because to the cutting-edge washing facilities that they have.

Top

The firm is one of the pioneers in the use of the most recent technology for top wear, which includes shirts for men, women, and children and children's shirts.

Active & Sports Wear

The woven apparel that is used for sports and athletic activities must be very durable in addition to being comfortable. Standard Group is able to manufacture the most long-lasting and comfortable sports and active wear imaginable since they have some of the most complicated machinery and their workforce is comprised of highly trained individuals.

Inner Wear

Within the realm of inner wear, comfort is of the utmost importance, and Standard Group employs the most advanced manufacturing methods and procures the most pleasant materials to guarantee that their products fulfill all requirements. In the course of many years, Standard Group has been manufacturing a wide range of different kinds of inner wear.

Outer Wear

Standard Group was established in 1984 specializing in the production of outerwear garments. Consequently, the firm has integrated the capacity to manufacture a wide range of outerwear. Through years of experience, their manufacturing teams have acquired expertise in outer wear.

Knitwear

The Standard Group's product line includes knitwear, which is one of the more recent additions to the assortment. At the moment, Standard Group is a leader in the manufacture of knit clothes that are both high in number and high in quality. In addition, Standard Group has established a robust quality assurance staff that is responsible for inspecting the clothing.

When it comes to knit production, even the most intricate patterns are now feasible because to the modern technologies that are used at Standard Group. They provide excellent quality at very reasonable costs.

Knit Products:

- Sweaters
- Pullover
- Cardigans
- Knitted Vest
- Tank Tops

Accessories

- Carton
- Poly bag
- Rib
- Belts
- Elastic
- Drawstring
- Elastic Draw cord
- Gum tape
- Cello tape
- Belt tape
- Twill tape
- Paper Sticker

➤ Label

Corporate Social Responsibility

One of the primary garment manufacturing companies in Bangladesh:

We prioritize responsible operations with the intention of contributing to society to the greatest extent possible. Many manufacturers look up to Standard Group as a model because they believe that by being socially responsible, they can set an example for others to follow and provide exponential benefits to society. By aligning our corporate social responsibility (CSR) services with national social and economic trends, we can contribute to the society we serve.

Some of the CSR projects by Standard Group:

Protection from mosquito borne diseases:

Employees are presented with brand new mosquito nets in order to prevent them from being exposed to potentially dangerous diseases such as dengue and malaria.

Loan provision:

Scholarships and loans for medical expenses are made available to members of the community.

Helping the poor:

Making sure that impoverished communities have access to warm clothes throughout the winter.

Human Resource Planning Process:

The textile and apparel sector places a significant emphasis on management practices. Considering the large number of workers, managing their workforce in the absence of an appropriate management system is challenging[15]. Standard Group adheres to a rigorous requirement procedure to get the most qualified employee. The HR department of this organization determines recruiting based on their specific requirements and then creates an appropriate job description. In addition, they compile a list of the most qualified prospects to be considered for interviews. Conducting interviews and assessing candidates based on their abilities is a demanding responsibility for HR professionals. The HR department also fulfils the crucial responsibility of offering direction and training to newly hired employees. Standard Group consistently implements strategic management strategies to enhance the well-being of its employees. The HR department upholds an annual promotion policy and promotes workers impartially. Ensuring equitable opportunities for all employees is of utmost importance. The use of effective HR practices within Standard Group fosters employee growth. This firm offers comprehensive medical benefits and housing allowances to all of its employees, demonstrating its commitment to exemplary human resources management. In addition, they provide an official transportation service and meals. In addition, this firm adheres to the Bangladesh Labor Law to uphold corporate policies and laws. Standard Group also handles the development of comprehensive compensation programs, which include bonuses, overtime pay, and profit sharing. Similarly, the HR department of this organization prioritizes non-monetary benefits such as sick breaks, job stability, growth opportunities, and maternity leave. In addition, HR workers monitor employees' Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and provide them with additional perks based on their performance metrics.

Forecasting

Through the examination of both the events that have occurred in the past and the current state of affairs, forecasting is the process of predicting what will occur in the future[16]. Forecasting, a strategic tool, is of utmost importance in managing the unpredictability of potential outcomes. It relies on historical and present data, as well as the examination of patterns and trends. The forecasting process is a key element used by the management of companies, government agencies, economists, and investors to decide resource allocation and produce reports. It is also a vital component in strategizing and preparing for expected expenditures. From a corporate perspective, this mostly relies on the anticipated demand for the company's products or services. For instance, economists may predict a certain variable, such as interest rates, at a given future date. Forecasting is akin to prediction, a broader word that includes other types of forecasts. It resembles, but is distinct from, futurology, which has a more comprehensive or holistic approach.

Process of Supply Chain Management

The phrase "supply chain management" refers to an all-encompassing strategy used to monitor the flow of raw materials into an organization, the internal processing of resources into completed products, and the distribution of finished goods to the end client. This method ensures that all of these processes are carried out efficiently[17]. Corporations have minimized their ownership of raw material suppliers and delivery networks to prioritize their expertise and increase adaptability. Outsourcing these operations is becoming more prevalent as other organizations can execute the activities more efficiently or at a lower cost. The impact has been to augment the number of businesses fulfilling client demand while diminishing managerial oversight of day-to-day logistical operations. One possible explanation for the development of supply chain management principles is that there has been a reduction in control and a rise in the number of partners involved in the supply chain. The purpose of supply chain management is to increase the level of trust and cooperation among the many stakeholders in the supply chain, which will ultimately result in an increase in the visibility and velocity of distribution of goods. Various models have been suggested to comprehend the actions necessary for managing the transfer of materials across different organizational and functional boundaries[18]. The actions that take place in the supply chain may be classified into three different levels: strategic, tactical, and operational.

Strategic

- The process of finding the appropriate number of warehouses, distribution hubs, and facilities, as well as their placement and configuration, is an essential part of strategic network optimization.
- Achieving a strategic relationship with suppliers, distributors, and consumers involves establishing effective communication channels to facilitate the exchange of important information and enhance operational efficiency. This may be achieved via practices such as cross docking, direct shipping, and using third-party logistics.
- Product design coordination involves ensuring that new and old goods are seamlessly integrated into the supply chain and effectively managed in terms of load.
- Information technology infrastructure is necessary to facilitate and enhance supply chain operations.

Tactical

- Procuring contracts and making other buying choices. 2. Making production choices, such as contracting, determining sites, scheduling, and defining planning processes. goods choices include determining the appropriate number, optimal placement, and desired quality of goods.
- Transportation strategy include the planning and implementation of several aspects such as the frequency of transportation, the selection of routes, and the establishment of contracts.
- Conducting a comprehensive evaluation of all activities in comparison to rivals and adopting the most effective strategies throughout the whole organization.

Operational

- A comprehensive coordination of manufacturing and distribution, which includes all of the components of the supply chain. The scheduling of production in real time for each individual manufacturing facility that is part of the supply chain
- Collaboratively organize sourcing activities, taking into account existing inventory and projected demand, with all suppliers.
- Inbound operations include the transportation of goods from suppliers and the process of receiving and managing inventories.
- Production operations include the use of resources and the movement of completed products.
- Outbound operations include all aspects of fulfilling client orders and transporting them to their destinations.

Functional Divisions of Standard Group

There are seven major departments under Standard Group. That are-

- Merchandising Department.
- Sampling Department.
- Commercial Department.
- Accessory Supply Department.
- Production Department.
- Distribution Department.
- Accounts Department.

Value Chain analysis of Standard Group

The success of a garment rests on the value it can provide. Value chain analysis is a valuable framework for methodically assessing the strengths and weaknesses of any firm. Value chain analysis operates on the assumption that a company comprises several activities essential for designing, producing, marketing, and supporting its product. Each of these activities can potentially enhance the value of the product or service, and each of these factors might serve as a distinct benefit for the company[19].

This value chain activity is divided in to two major categories-

- Primary activity
- Supportive activity.

Figure 1: Value chain of the firm.

Inbound Logistics

- Firm’s effectiveness.

Operation

- The level of productivity of the staff in comparison to the productivity of the Standard Group’s significant rivals.
- The effectiveness of the services Standard Group (SGA).
- Evaluation of the efficiency of the service control systems used by Standard Group in order to enhance quality and decrease costs.
- It is efficient to plan the layout and create the process as well.

Outbound Logistics

- When it comes to the delivery of completed products and services, the Standard Group is known for its punctuality and efficiency.
- Productivity in the transportation of completed products is a crucial aspect.

Marketing and sales

- It is the efficiency of market research in determining the different client categories and their requirements.
- A novel approach to promoting and advertising products and services.
- Motivating human resource capital is a crucial aspect.
- One of the goals of the company is to cultivate a positive image and reputation.
- In addition, it encompasses the devotion of its consumers to the brand.
- The extent of market dominance within a certain market sector or the whole market.

Customers

- Customer input solicitation refers to the act of seeking feedback from customers in order to enhance the quality of service.
- The company's promptness in addressing client issues is commendable.

Procurement

- The Standard Group is now engaged in the active pursuit of alternate sources of raw materials to decrease their dependence on a one supplier.
- The organization aims to acquire raw materials promptly, at the most economical price, and with an acceptable standard of quality.
- The process of acquiring plant, equipment, and buildings.
- Its enduring partnership with a dependable provider.

Firm Infrastructure

- Its capacity to discover new product markets.
- Opportunities and possible environmental threats are also present.
- To accomplish the business purpose, the quality of the strategic planning system is of utmost importance.
- It takes into account the coordination and integration of all operations associated with the value chain among the various subunits of the company.
- One of its strengths is its capacity to acquire financing at relatively cheap costs for both capital expenditures and operating capital.
- In terms of making strategic and regular decisions, the amount of information systems at its disposal provides help.

Current Backward Supply Chain in Standard Group

Reverse logistics is a crucial aspect of a ready-made garment (RMG) manufacturing[20]. When a factory relies on external suppliers, it encounters many issues that result in a very unpredictable manufacturing process and product delivery. The knit garments unit of Standard Group is organized on a vertically composite structure. Consequently, Standard Group is not burdened by the typical issues other small firms encounter. However, in actuality, Standard Group's whole downward supply chain system cannot meet all the requirements of the garment unit due to the existence of various kinds of raw materials that Standard Group is incapable of producing.

Backward Supply Chain

Figure 2: Backward Supply Chain of the firm.

Cotton

Cotton from:

- USA (Fair Trade certified cotton, Organic cotton)
- CIS countries (Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan)
- African(CMIA cotton, Aid by Trade Foundation certified countries)
- Pakistan Issues concerned
- Certificate from Aid by Trade Foundation
- Certificate of OEKO standard
- Certificate of Reach Standard
- Textile Organic Exchange
- Textile Global Organic standard
- Child labor
- Cotton plucking procedure

The spinning division of Standard Group mostly supplies its products to its affiliated knitting subsidiary. However, in instances when the knitting unit's demand is minimal, yarn is sold to external firms that focus on exporting. Usually, knitting accounts for 93% of the output of the spinning unit[21].

Yarn and Thread

Standard Group only manufactures 100% cotton yarn specifically for knit fabrics. Additional yarn varieties required for knit fabrics are procured from other suppliers. Seventy-five per cent of these yarns are sourced from local firms, while the remaining 25% are imported from international suppliers, mostly Chinese. Our sourcing strategy for sewing threads is as diverse as our product range. We procure all varieties from both domestic and international manufacturers, ensuring we have the right thread for every fabric and design.

Figure 3: Types of yarn and thread that is outsourced

Knitting

The knitting unit of Standard Group utilizes yarn to produce knit fabric, with a monthly capacity of 600 tons of grey knit fabric. The existing machine capacity is used for fabric production for external firms, similar to how Standard Group produces knit fabric at other plants. This reciprocal collaboration arises because the machines in the Standard Group have different diameters and features, and the internal machines are unable to create all the necessary knit textiles. Only a small quantity of woven fabric is required for clothing.

Booking fabric in advance is required, with a lead time ranging from 30 to 90 days, depending on the fabric type and machine availability. Occasionally, the lead time might be affected by the availability of yarn[22].

Dyeing

The Standard Group's dyeing plant produces around 900 tons of colored cloth monthly, with a daily output capacity of around 30 tons. This equipment is only capable of dyeing knit fabric. The Standard Group's dyeing unit is now operating at a satisfactory level, consistently meeting the garment unit's needs within the specified time frame in most situations.

Washing

Preceding and after the creation of clothing, it is important to engage in washing. Before being used in clothes, some materials undergo a washing process for practical reasons, whereas other garments are cleaned after manufacturing. The washing facility of Standard Group has a daily capacity of 18,000 pieces, with two shifts, each lasting eight hours. The capacity of the dryer is influenced by factors such as the kind of cloth, the type of wash, and the amount of items being dried. If required, the washing machine operates beyond regular working hours. The washing machine has a lead time of 6 hours for the washing process and 1.5 hours for the drying process.

Printing

The printing apparatus has a color capacity of 18 hues and is capable of printing 0.5-0.6 million pieces (in critical situations) and 1-1.2 million pieces (in regular circumstances) of fabric every month. The possible printing options here include:

Figure 4: Different types of printing done at Standard Group printing unit

The main problem with this printing unit is the quality and timeliness of the delivery.

Analysis and Findings

The data obtained for this research were analyzed using Likert's Summative Rating scale. This scale was used to facilitate the development of tables for data analysis and to ensure the reliability of the data. The variables have been rated using the mean rating. Likert's Summative Rating technique was used to analyze the questions in this study's questionnaire. The allocated weight to the different choices is as follows: Strongly Agree = 5, Agree = 4, Neutral = 3. Disagree is assigned a value of 2, whereas Strongly Disagree is assigned a value of 1.

Production

Order lead time of The Standard Group is good enough to compare with the industry's order lead time.

Table 1 Production related

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage of Frequency
Strongly Agree	15	30%
Agree	22	44%
Neutral	08	16%
Disagree	05	10%
Strongly Disagree	0	0%
Total	50	100%

Figure 5: Production related

The data collected for this study were evaluated using Likert's Summative Rating scale. This scale was used to expedite the creation of tables for data analysis and to guarantee the dependability of the data. The factors have been evaluated based on the average rating. Likert's Summative Rating approach was used to examine the questions in the questionnaire for this research. The assigned weight to each option is as follows: A rating of 5 corresponds to "Strongly Agree," a rating of 4 corresponds to "Agree," and a rating of 3 corresponds to "Neutral."

The value of 2 is allocated to "Disagree", whereas the value of 1 is assigned to "Strongly Disagree."

Table 2: Production related

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage of Frequency
Strongly Agree	13	26%
Agree	23	46%
Neutral	10	20%
Disagree	04	08%
Strongly Disagree	0	0%
Total	50	100%

Figure 6: Production related

Based on the survey, around 72% of the participants strongly agree or agree that the production management department maintains consistent communication with the marketing and distribution departments, positively impacting the supply chain. The data indicates that The Standard Group's supply chain performs moderately in production management. The corporation has a manufacturing facility that ensures sufficient production capability to satisfy substantial demand levels.

Table 3: Production related

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage of Frequency
Strongly Agree	26	52%
Agree	20	40%
Neutral	04	08%
Disagree	0	0%
Strongly Disagree	0	0%
Total	50	100%

Figure 7: Production related

Based on the information provided, 92% of the respondents highly agree that the firm has a manufacturing facility that guarantees enough output during periods of high demand. The strong performance of The Standard Group's supply chain is seen in its manufacturing facilities.

Inventory Management: The inventory management department ensures that there are sufficient stocks to support continuous manufacturing.

Table 4: Inventory management related

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage of Frequency
Strongly Agree	18	36%
Agree	19	38%
Neutral	07	14%
Disagree	03	06%
Strongly Disagree	03	06%
Total	50	100%

Figure 8: Inventory management related

Based on the information provided, about 74% of the participants agree or strongly agree that the inventory management department effectively manages sufficient supplies to ensure ongoing production. The Standard Group's inventory management demonstrates satisfactory performance throughout its supply chain.

Forecasting: The current forecasting technology can properly anticipate the price of raw materials.

Table 5: Forecasting related

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage of Frequency
Strongly Agree	02	04%
Agree	04	08%
Neutral	16	32%
Disagree	22	44%
Strongly Disagree	06	12%
Total	50	100%

Figure 9 Forecasting related

Based on the data provided, 12% of the respondents strongly agree or agree that the existing forecasting system can properly estimate the price of raw materials. Conversely, 56% of the respondents strongly disagree or disagree with this

statement. Regarding price predictions, The Standard Group's supply chain is underperforming. Current forecasting systems can predict future buyer demand.

Table 6: Forecasting related

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage of Frequency
Strongly Agree	23	46%
Agree	20	40%
Neutral	05	10%
Disagree	02	04%
Strongly Disagree	0	0%
Total	50	100%

Figure 10: Forecasting related

Based on the data provided, around 86% of the respondents agree or strongly agree that the inventory management department maintains regular contact with the production department. This level of communication contributes to the moderate performance of the supply chain in the Standard Group. The inventory management department regularly contacts the manufacturing department.

Table 7: Communication related

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage of Frequency
Strongly Agree	24	48%
Agree	21	42%
Neutral	05	10%
Disagree	0	0%
Strongly Disagree	0	0%
Total	50	100%

Figure 11: Communication related

The data indicates that over 90% of participants agree or strongly agree with the regular communication between the inventory management and production departments. This effective communication contributes to the good performance of the supply chain within the Standard Group. The existing supply chain facilitates the acquisition of valuable input from the vendors.

Table 8: Communication related

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage of Frequency
Strongly Agree	02	04%
Agree	06	12%
Neutral	10	20%
Disagree	22	44%
Strongly Disagree	10	20%
Total	50	100%

Figure 12: Communication related

Based on the information provided, only 64% of the respondent's express strong disagreement or disagreement with the effectiveness of the present supply chain in collecting valuable input from suppliers. The supply chain is not effectively soliciting input from suppliers. The current supply chain management often leads to regular contact among supply chain participants.

Table 9: Communication related

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage of Frequency
Strongly Agree	0	0%
Agree	17	34%
Neutral	23	46%
Disagree	10	20%
Strongly Disagree	0	0%
Total	50	100%

Figure 13: Communication related

According to the study, just 34% of respondents agree and strongly agree that the existing supply chain enables quicker, simpler, and more frequent contact among supply chain partners. The mean indicates that the supply chain has a subpar performance in this specific metric.

Order Placement

The existing supply chain system enables a decrease in the time it takes to respond within the supply chain, resulting in quicker placing of orders.

Table 10: Order placement related

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage of Frequency
Strongly Agree	21	42%
Agree	19	38%
Neutral	10	20%
Disagree	0	0%
Strongly Disagree	0	0%
Total	50	100%

Figure 14: Order placement related

Upon analyzing the table, it becomes evident that over 80% of the participants agree or strongly agree that the existing supply chain system enables a decrease in reaction time within the supply chain, resulting in quicker order placing. The data suggests that The Standard Group's supply chain has a modest level of performance when it comes to placing orders. The customer order path is simple

Table 11: Customer order related

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage of Frequency
Strongly Agree	12	24%
Agree	19	38%
Neutral	09	18%
Disagree	07	14%
Strongly Disagree	03	06%
Total	50	100%

Figure 15: Customer order related

Based on the data provided, it is evident that more than 62% of the participants highly concur and believe that the customer order process is straightforward and efficient. The simplicity of the order placement process in the Standard group implies customer satisfaction. Overall, the supply chain of the Standard group performs somewhat well in terms of the order placement method.

Managing Distribution

Statement 12: Shipments are delivered as per the dateline.

Table 12: Distribution related

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage of Frequency
Strongly Agree	28	56%
Agree	15	30%
Neutral	04	08%
Disagree	03	06%
Strongly Disagree	0	0%
Total	50	100%

Figure 16: Distribution related

Based on the information provided, it is evident that 86% of the respondents strongly agree or agree that shipments are delivered on time. The delivery supply chain of The Standard Group is very efficient. Distribution system is flexible enough to meet particular customer demands

Table 13: Distribution system related

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage of Frequency
Strongly Agree	11	22%
Agree	23	46%
Neutral	09	18%
Disagree	04	08%
Strongly Disagree	03	06%
Total	50	100%

Figure 17: Distribution system related

Based on the investigation, it was discovered that around 68% of the respondents expressed strong agreement or agreement with the flexibility of the distribution system in meeting specific consumer requests.

Conclusion:

The Ready-Made-Garment (RMG) business significantly contributes to Bangladesh's overall development. In today's economic world, no significant participant in the garment sector can overlook Bangladesh's capacity to provide high-quality and valuable items. Standard Group, a prominent clothing company in Bangladesh, began operations in 1984. The firm has seen substantial growth in its size and client base over the years. The firm has internal facilities for clothing washing, printing, embroidery, apparel design, garment testing, and manufacture of different accessories. Their garment manufacturing setup and services in Bangladesh are equipped with state-of-the-art technology. The firm consistently offers consumers a clothing-sourcing solution, together with production facilities. Supply chains are efficient when the exchange value of the system meets the expectations of the parties involved in the supply chain. The current corporate landscape is characterized by increased globalization and intense competition compared to previous times. Contemporary businesses are distinguished by shorter durations of product viability, rapid launches of new products, and a consumer base that is ever more aware, well-informed, and sophisticated. This compels supply networks to become more efficient. Standard Group may enhance customer service by implementing strategic measures to address inefficient supply chain regions. Standard Group plays a pivotal position in the local and worldwide clothing sector. These industries provide a substantial contribution to the economic sector.

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